

**NEW VEGETABLE, FOOL AND POTATO CROPS RESOURCES,
MECHANIZED AGROTECHNOLOGIES**

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Annotation: *This article discusses the benefits of drip irrigation, which is one of the main agro-technical measures in agriculture, the importance of saving water resources given.*

Keywords: *vegetables, melons, garden, resource saving, technology, drip irrigation, drip irrigation, fertilizer, efficiency.*

The role and importance of the agricultural sector in ensuring food security of the world's population is growing day by day. In particular, it is important to use the available resources and opportunities in our country, to provide the population with agricultural products, to increase productivity or interest, to introduce scientific achievements and modern approaches to the field. In his Address to the Oliy Majlis on December 29, 2020, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev called for poverty reduction and rural development.

They emphasized that the most effective way to increase incomes was to dramatically increase productivity and efficiency in agriculture. In this process, the priority has been to increase the income per hectare from the current average of \$ 2,000 to at least \$ 5,000, and to make agriculture the most advanced technologies, water-saving and biotechnologies, seed production, achievements in science and innovation.

Drip irrigation to the root zone of the plant in the care of agricultural crops it is an irrigation method that delivers the right amount of water to its needs. In drip irrigation it will be possible to provide the plant with uninterrupted water and nutrients depending on demand. During the entire irrigation period, the supply of water saturated with mineral fertilizers is irrigated to create an optimal order in the root feeding layer of the soil according to the water consumption of the crop and increases the productivity of agricultural crops excess water should not be added to groundwater when drip irrigation technology is introduced.

As a result, secondary salinization of soils is prevented. In addition,

- set the irrigation regime according to the plant's demand for water;
- Reducing evaporating water from the soil;
- All water should be for crops only as there are no weeds;

- Ensure that water does not spread across the field and seep into the soil

The total water savings are on average 2.6 thousand m³ (40-50%) for 1 hectare of cotton, 1.3 thousand m³ (30-40%) for 1 hectare of wheat and for 1 hectare of orchard 1.8 thousand m³ (40-50%)

At the same time, the use of drip irrigation on sloping areas is very effective, as it does not lead to soil erosion. Also, when watering with a simple mesoile application of this technology in hilly areas due to the possibility of soil subsidence and void formation is very effective.

Drip irrigation creates optimal conditions for plant growth, as a result of which it spends more than 70% of its energy on productivity, yields increase by an average of 40-50%, and field development is the same.

Also, the amount of water needed by the plant, water is not lost for disposal and filtration. Irrigation equipment can increase the efficiency of up to 98%

As a result of direct application of mineral fertilizers to the root system of plants in drip irrigation, the absorption of mineral fertilizers by crops reaches 90-95%. Also, because the fertilizer is given along with the water, the entry of tractors into the field is reduced. This is fuel lubrication saves on material consumption. As a result of drip irrigation of water and nutrients in accordance with the requirements of crops, the average yield in orchards and vineyards increases by 50-60%, in vegetable crops – 50-70%.

Also, the crops ripen 10–15 days earlier and the yield is the same throughout the area. In addition, there is no land for the return of machinery and water management at the headwaters and foothills of the canal, ditch.

Irrigation uses an average of 250 kg of nitrogen, 150 kg of phosphorus, 100 kg of potassium fertilizers per 1 hectare of cotton field, and only 25-30 of these mineral fertilizers are used. The remaining mineral fertilizers evaporate into the air and are discharged into the aquifer and into the collector-drainage water through the groundwater table. In drip irrigation, mineral fertilizers are absorbed and applied directly to the root layer during irrigation, which increases the rate of mineral fertilization by 90-95%.

At the same time, nutrients are absorbed quickly and rapidly which is the most effective way to fertilize in dry climates. Also, due to the fact that weeds are not supplemented and their seeds do not ripen, there is no field distribution, as a result of which the crop area in 2-3 years completely cleared of weeds. Currently, if 1 irrigator is needed for every 5 hectares of land to carry out conventional irrigation, 1 drip irrigator can irrigate 20-25 hectares and more.

In addition, there is no need to prepare the field for irrigation, that is, to prepare grass, cellophane and other equipment. Water management and control walks between branches will be eliminated (Table 1).

In addition, land is not allocated for the operation of equipment in the ditches, ditches, headwaters and fields, as well as for water management along the fields. As a result, land use efficiency will increase.

Comparison table of productivity in drip irrigation

Crop type	Average yield In irrigation	Average yield Drip in irrigation	%
Bitter pepper	12 tons	18 tons	50
Onion	30 tons	60 tons	100
Tomato	25 tons	50 tons	100
Cucumber	15 tons	30 tons	100

As a result, the cost of mineral fertilizers will be reduced and an average of 450,000 soums will be saved per hectare of cotton and 500,000 soums per hectare of vegetable crops per year. In recent years, the government has paid great attention to the widespread introduction of drip irrigation technology.

In addition, many benefits are provided in drip irrigation, focusing on the effective application of mineral fertilizers. With the introduction of drip irrigation technology, the costs will be covered in cotton for 3 years, vegetables and other crops for 2-2.5 years. The investment in horticulture is the most profitable, and the payback period is less than 2 years. , local containers can be used for fertilization, as well as annuals can be used for 2-3 years by collecting irrigation tapes used in crops

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